

The Axon Disinhibition Mechanism: The Future Of Brain Research?

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Abstract:

This paper introduces the Axon Disinhibition Mechanism (ADM), a new theoretical framework to account for cognitive phenomena like emotional irrationality and intuition, with experimentally testable predictions. By proposing a specific mechanism, ADM provides a clear target for experimental testing and verification of predicted neuronal activity patterns. It enhances the ability to validate or refine the theory through systematic empirical investigation. ADM proposes that human cognition arises from combinatorial coding and disinhibition of specific neural patterns at the axon hillocks of neurons. Rather than simple summation, neurons recognize patterns, using factors like genetic information, structural proteins, neurochemicals and electrophysiological states through a process akin to odor detection. That the process creates multifactor memories in each neuron. Matching of incoming neural activity to such memories is proposed to trigger disinhibition of GABA neurons and axonal firing, while mismatches leave neurons inhibited. The binary neural disinhibition outputs across vast populations is theorized to convey meaning and subjective experience. We discuss the key tenets of ADM. While highly speculative, ADM offers an intriguing pattern recognition perspective that warrants further investigation. The author acknowledges the assistance of Claude, an AI system, in helping to research background information, structure and draft sections of this paper.

Introduction:

Despite incredible advances, neuroscience still lacks comprehensive theories fully explaining the neural basis of subjective experience, consciousness and higher cognition (Chalmers, 1995). The Axon Disinhibition Mechanism (ADM) proposes a new overarching framework integrating neurobiological, electrophysiological and quantum phenomena to derive these higher cognitive abilities from first principles of neural information processing (Hameroff 2014).

The Core Premise of ADM:

At its core, ADM posits that neurons do not simply sum their incoming signals and fire action potentials once a threshold is reached. Rather, it hypothesizes a vastly more complex integration process that occurs at the axon hillock region:

- 1) Neurons encode combinatorial "memories" based on specific patterns of factors like:
 - Genetic regulatory codes governing protein expression
 - Structural conformations of cytoskeletal proteins like microtubules
 - Concentrations and distributions of specific neurochemicals/neurotransmitters
 - Electrophysiological parameters like sub-threshold membrane potentials
 - Unique combinations of synaptic inputs from other neurons
- 2) Incoming neural activity patterns at the millions of synapses are integrated by the process to add to and compare with these stored combinatorial memories.
- 3) In neurons where the incoming signal pattern sufficiently matches the encoded memories, a mechanism disinhibits local GABA neurons, removing inhibition and allowing the axon to fire.
- 4) Neurons whose inputs do not match the combinatorial memory pattern remain inhibited and do not fire.
- 5) The binary ADM output of disinhibited (firing) pattern across the vast neural network is hypothesized to convey meaning, forming the basis of subjective experiences, intuition and consciousness.

The binary ADM output of disinhibited (firing) pattern is proposed to underlie perception, cognition, emotional processing and meta-cognitive states like consciousness and self-awareness (Deco 2014). ADM is portrayed as the "steel framework" that is overlaid by highly distributed combinatorial coding and pattern recognition processes,

adding to the mystery of the mind. Evidence of the binary framework lies in the highly researched timing of neural processes (Rolls, 2007) as well as the verifiable controlling power of neural regions (Miller 2001).

ADM proposes that an executive control center, the prefrontal cortex regions, the limbic system and the primitive brainstem centers rapidly switch control in milliseconds to manage the neural system (Lau 2011). Sensory perceptions are recognized by the association cortical regions as objects and events (Olshausen 1996). Event recognition can lead to conflicts. For example, the amygdala recognizes a snake and triggers visceral responses within 20 milliseconds (LeDoux, 1998). The prefrontal regions then identify it as a harmless garden hose around 300 milliseconds later and inhibit the tensed emotional regions (Eisenberger 2004). Even the executive control centers can be overruled by the amygdala in some cases (Pessoa, 2008).

Try this thought experiment: Can you willfully raise your hand? Yes, when sitting quietly alone. But suppose you are in an elevator with other passengers - then raising your arm would be socially inappropriate. Even with the intention of conducting this scientific test, your willful action may be blocked in that situation by other neural constraints related to context. If you continue with such experiments, you find that willful actions can be overruled when they are not Worthwhile, Appropriate, Safe, or Practical (WASP criteria). The control system is managed by the decision-making circuitry of the Papez circuit, with its feedback/feedforward loops.

Similarly, the neuroscience points to the claustrum as a key region involved in the neural processes underlying conscious awareness (Crick 2005). Recently, studies have captured the mechanisms at the pivotal point where nerve impulses culminate into conscious thoughts (Koch 2007). Objects or events in the real world have many attributes, including color, shape, distance, velocity, smell, sound and tactile properties. A PET study by Hadjikhani revealed the involvement of the claustrum in cross-modal integration - tasks requiring simultaneous evaluation of information from more than one sensory domain (Hadjikhani 2008). Without this region, the subject may still respond to simple, isolated or highly familiar stimuli, but not to complex or unfamiliar inputs (Goll et al., 2015). The claustrum appears to enable the unified conscious experience, where objects and events are perceived in an integrated manner rather than as isolated attributes (Graziano, 2013). It acts as a "dashboard" displaying integrated thoughts to consciousness.

The emerging view is that the brain makes decisions via the neural control processes, while conscious awareness passively observes and receives the output signals (Boly et al., 2017). Brain function can override conscious will, such as preventing physically risky actions (Baumeister et al., 2009). Consciousness is not the primary decision-maker, and even willful intentions are limited by the brain prioritizing safety and rational constraints (Haggard, 2008). Conscious volition is more of a desire state rather than an executive function (Shepherd, 2015). Intuition enables the brain to make rapid decisions in as little as 20 milliseconds, with the conscious awareness following around 350 milliseconds later (Hodgkin 1952). Benjamin Libet's famous experiments found that motor neurons fired 350ms before subjects reported their conscious decision to press a button (Libet 1983). If such precise temporal delays between unconscious brain activity and conscious perception can be measured, as Libet showed, it challenges views of consciousness as a separate spiritual entity driving cognition (Chalmers, 1995).

Multi-Level Substrate for Cognition:

A key distinction of ADM is that rather than only electrophysiological dynamics, it incorporates diverse biological levels into the informational substrate. The combinatorial memory is encoded in structural proteins like microtubules interacting with gene expression, neurochemicals, electrical fields and synaptic inputs (Rowlands 2017). ADM theorizes that quantum phenomena like coherence in microtubules could enable vastly more information encoding capacity and powerful pattern matching abilities in "quantum neurons" compared to classical models (Hameroff 2014).

ADM's Explanatory Power:

Proponents argue ADM holds explanatory promise for several cognitive phenomena that current models struggle with:

1) Intuitions and "Non-Logical" Cognition:

Intuition is framed as an emergent property of the match/mismatch patterns across the neural network. Purely rational processes depend on specific sub-networks, but intuitive leaps can arise when radically new input combinations trigger neural disinhibition cascades.

2) Emotional "Irrationality":

Intense emotions like fear or anger are hypothesized to arise from global disinhibition cascades overpowering the logical reasoning networks. Runaway neural firings corresponding to the emotional state override other inhibitions through volume transmission of neurochemicals.

3) Subjective Experience and Consciousness:

The specific ever-changing patterns of disinhibited/inhibited neurons integrating multi-level informational states is proposed as the neurological basis of the richness of subjective conscious perception and experience.

4) Memory "Feelings" and Intuitions:

Incomplete matches between current inputs and combinatorial memories are theorized to produce partial disinhibition patterns giving rise to intuitive "feelings" of recognition and vague associations.

5) Mind-Body Connections:

Observers note ADM could potentially explain bizarre phenomena like memories seemingly transferred through organ transplants. If memories utilize quantum and biochemical levels, proteins/molecules from transplants could encode residual "traces" interacting with recipient neural networks.

Experimental Testing of ADM:

To transition from an intriguing theoretical framework to an accepted model, ADM will require extensive empirical testing and validation through carefully designed experiments. Some key predictions and avenues to probe ADM include:

1) Electrical Recording:

Combine advanced multi-electrode arrays, patch-clamp electrophysiology and voltage-sensitive dyes to detect proposed combinatorial coding and binary disinhibition/inhibition patterns across neuron populations during higher cognition compared to passive states. Confirm if predicted binary spiking patterns are observed (Nicoletis 2003).

2) Neural Perturbation:

Use optogenetics, chemogenetics or targeted electromagnetic stimulation to force specific sub-populations of neurons into disinhibited or inhibited states. Record resulting conscious experiences and behavior to map disinhibition patterns to subjective states (Tye 2012).

3) Quantum Effects:

Leverage advanced quantum biology techniques to detect proposed quantum coherence in microtubules. Determine if disruption of coherence impairs pattern matching and higher cognition compared to anesthetic mechanisms (Koch, 2022).

4) Cytoskeleton Manipulation:

Genetically or pharmacologically manipulate cytoskeletal structures like microtubules to disrupt their conformational encoding. Assess impact on memory, cognition and conscious perception (Shima 2007).

5) Neural Network Simulations:

Build computational neural network models implementing the combinatorial coding and binary disinhibition mechanics of ADM. Test their ability to exhibit analogues of human intuition, subjective experience, emotional irrationality compared to traditional artificial neural networks (Hinton 2006).

While definitive evidence is still lacking, the potential of ADM to provide an integrated multi-level account spanning neurobiology, physics, and cognitive phenomena warrants focused investigation going forward (Maguire 2015).

Conclusion:

The Axon Disinhibition Mechanism offers an ambitious novel neural information processing framework for understanding consciousness and higher cognition. By proposing specific combinatorial coding mechanisms at axon hillocks integrating genetic, biochemical, structural, electrophysiological and environmental factors, ADM takes a distinctive multi-level integrative systems perspective. The binary disinhibition outputs across neural networks are put forth as the basis of intuition, subjective experience, emotions and conscious perception.

While highly speculative currently, ADM's explanatory scope is thought-provoking and it makes several testable predictions. Careful, unbiased empirical investigation and computational modeling efforts will be crucial to determine if the unconventional ideas in ADM simply reflect an appealing but incorrect theory, or whether they contain kernels of a new biological truth about how cognition and consciousness actually emerge from neural information processing.

Pioneering hypotheses stretching the boundaries of our scientific understanding should be approached with open-mindedness tempered by appropriate skepticism. The burden of proof rests firmly on ADM's proponents to conclusively validate its major premises through rigorous experimentation and incremental accumulation of evidence. Only through such scrutiny can truly paradigm-shifting science advance (Churchland, 2006).

ADM stands as an intriguing conceptual launch point catalyzing deeper multidisciplinary exploration into the neural underpinnings of the seemingly irreducible mysteries of human subjective experience. The ultimate scientific legacy of this ambitious framework remains to be collectively determined through rational discourse, imaginative experimentation and an unwavering commitment to empirical facts (Baars & Franklin, 2003).

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